

BRIEF REPORT ON THE FORECAST OF THE EXISTENCE OF NEW PARTICLES POSSIBLY DETECTABLE THROUGH THE ARCA MASSIVE TELESCOPES OF THE KM3NeT PROJECT.

The structure of ARCA detectors installation off the Sicilian coast as part of the KM3NeT project, made possible the capture of the KM3 230213A event, of the arrival of a neutrino with an energy of 220 PeV, among others.

This places the KM3NeT project at a very advanced stage in the detection of very high-energy neutrinos.

But precisely for this reason, it is also in a privileged position to detect new particles created by special interactions of high-energy neutrinos in collisions, if methods specifically designed and developed for this purpose are elaborated.

The Energy Layers Theory, or Layers Theory for short, predicts the existence of three types of particles, whose sizes would bridge the abyss between the sizes of the neutrino and the electron; furthermore, by virtue of energy layers, it also predicts the existence of eight other types of particles, whose sizes would be smaller, some much smaller, than neutrinos themselves.

The Energy Layers Theory is part of The Theory of the Configuration of the Energy which I published in 2010.

It establishes that in the quantum order, the smallest particles would be made-up of energy fields located in layers or levels, and the number of them would determine the final size of the particle, and their relative values between layers would obey an exponential function.

(For more and in-depth information, contact to joseluisdefez58@gmail.com).

The KM3NeT project has the possibility to carry out the actual detection of the particles predicted in the aforementioned Theory.